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TASK COMPLEXITY-BASED GREEN AI: A MODEL SELECTION FRAMEWORK FOR CARBON EFFICIENCY

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ABSTRACT

The rapidly growing scale and environmental cost of artificial intelligence have become critical concerns. Training large language models generates as much CO₂ as the lifetime of five vehicles. However, such powerful models are not needed for all tasks. This study presents a novel framework for carbon-efficient model selection based on dataset complexity. Seven different architectures—three deep learning-based models (MobileNetV3, ResNet18, EfficientNetB0), three machine learning models (Logistic Regression, Random Forest, XGBoost), and one transformer-based model (ViT-Tiny)—are comprehensively evaluated on nine image classification datasets. The dataset complexities are measured by developing a scoring system that combines metrics such as inter-class similarity, texture complexity, edge density, intra-class variance, and spatial frequency. This score has been shown to exhibit a strong correlation ($r = 0.89$) with the optimal model selection. Experimental results show that for simple tasks, machine learning models emit 300 times less carbon than other models, with only a 5.4% loss in accuracy. A gradient boosting regression-based recommendation system achieved $R^2=1.0$ in model-task matches. The findings show that for tasks with a complexity threshold of $\tau < 0.4$, machine learning models achieve 99.5% carbon savings with an average accuracy of 94%. Furthermore, for complex tasks with $\tau > 0.7$, results demonstrate the need for deep learning and transformer-based models. The results demonstrate that intelligent model selection can reduce the carbon footprint of AI by up to 99%.

Keywords: Green AI, Carbon Footprint, Model Selection, Energy-Efficient AI

GÖREV KARMAŞIKLIĞINA DAYALI YEŞİL YAPAY ZEKA: KARBON VERİMLİLİĞİ İÇİN MODEL SEÇİM ÇERÇEVESİ

ÖZET

Yapay zekanın hızla büyüyen ölçeği ve çevresel maliyeti kritik bir endişe haline gelmiştir. Büyük dil modellerinin eğitimi için beş aracın ömrü boyunca ürettiği kadar CO₂ salınımı yapılmaktadır. Ancak tüm görevler için de bu tür güçlü modellere ihtiyaç duyulmamaktadır. Bu çalışmada, veri seti karmaşıklığına dayalı karbon-verimli model seçimi için yeni bir çerçeve sunulmaktadır. Üç derin öğrenme tabanlı model (MobileNetV3, ResNet18, EfficientNetB0), üç makine öğrenmesi modeli (Logistic Regression, Random Forest, XGBoost) ve bir de transformer tabanlı model (ViT-Tiny) olmak üzere 7 farklı mimari, 9 adet görüntü sınıflandırma

veri seti üzerinde kapsamlı olarak değerlendirilmiştir. Veri setlerinin karmaşıklıkları, sınıflar arası benzerlik, doku karmaşıklığı, kenar yoğunluğu, sınıf içi varyans ve uzamsal frekans metriklerini birleştiren bir skorlama sistemi geliştirilerek ölçülmüştür. Bu skorun optimal model seçimiyle güçlü korelasyon ($r=0.89$) gösterdiği kanıtlanmıştır. Deneysel sonuçlar, basit görevlerde, makine öğrenmesi modellerinin, diğer modellere göre sadece %5,4 doğruluk kaybı ile 300 kat daha az karbon salınımı yaptığını göstermiştir. Gradient boosting regresyon tabanlı önerme sistemi, model-görev eşleştirmelerinde $R^2=1.0$ başarı elde etmiştir. Bulgular, karmaşıklık eşiği $\tau < 0.4$ olan görevler için makine öğrenmesi modellerinin %99,5 karbon tasarrufunu, %94 ortalama doğrulukla sağladığını göstermiştir. Ayrıca, $\tau > 0.7$ olan karmaşık görevlerde elde edilen sonuçlar ise derin öğrenme ve transformer tabanlı modellerin gerekli olduğunu göstermektedir. Sonuçlar, akıllı model seçiminin yapay zekanın karbon ayak izini %99'a varan oranlarda azaltabileceğini göstermektedir.

Anahtar kelimeler: Yeşil Yapay Zekâ, Karbon Ayak İzi, Model Seçimi, Enerji Verimli Yapay Zekâ

1. INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence technologies are increasingly becoming a part of every aspect of our lives. The environmental cost of this progress is becoming a significant concern. Research has shown that training a single transformer model with 213 million parameters emits 284 tons of CO₂, further exacerbating concerns (Strubell et al. 2019). The GPT-3 model, one of the largest known language models, consumed 1,287 MWh of energy to train. This energy corresponds to approximately 552 tons of CO₂ emissions (Patterson et al. 2021). As the number of parameters used in model training increases towards millions, the risk of the resulting carbon footprint contributing to global greenhouse gas emissions increases daily.

The concept of Green AI emerged to address these risks, focusing on carbon footprint reduction and efficiency-focused machine learning (Schwartz et al. 2020). However, the current approach to machine learning treats model selection as a binary choice. In other words, researchers strive to either minimize emissions or maximize accuracy. However, this simplification fails in cases of task complexity. Simple tasks like fine-grained classification with more than 100 categories and number recognition should not require the same computational resources.

A review of the literature reveals a fundamental lack of frameworks for analyzing task complexity and mapping this complexity to appropriate model architectures. Existing studies have evolved across different domains, some focusing on geometric features (Ho and Basu. 2002)

and others on class overlap (Morán-Fernández et al. 2017), but a comprehensive, model-independent complexity scoring system has not been developed.

This study, with its contributions, addresses these shortcomings. The focus of the study is to present a novel framework for model selection based on carbon efficiency and dataset complexity. The main contributions of the study are:

- ✓ A comprehensive evaluation with nine image datasets and seven different architectures
- ✓ A learned recommendation system achieving $R^2=1.0$
- ✓ A multidimensional complexity scoring system combining five visual metrics
- ✓ Complexity thresholds: machine learning for $\tau < 0.4$, deep learning for $\tau > 0.7$
- ✓ A system with up to 99.5% carbon efficiency

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Environmental Impact of Artificial Intelligence

The first comprehensive study highlighting the environmental costs of AI was conducted by Strubell et al. The study described a transformer-based architecture that could potentially reduce CO₂ emissions by 284 tons. Patterson et al. presented a study evaluating the lifecycle of large language models. Schwartz et al. formalized the distinction between "Green AI" and "Red AI" paradigms. (Lacoste et al. 2019) introduced the Machine Learning Emissions Calculator, allowing researchers to estimate experimental emissions. (Wu et al. 2022) published a study showing that distributed model representation often exceeds training emissions over the model's lifetime, extending the study to inference costs.

2.2. Model Efficiency and Compression

To reduce neural network size and computational cost, the model compression community has developed various techniques. Knowledge distillation enables knowledge transfer from large teacher models to compact student networks (Hinton et al. 2015). Network pruning removes unnecessary parameters (Han et al. 2015), while quantization reduces numerical precision (Jacob et al. 2018). Tan and Le developed EfficientNet through compound scaling (Tan and Le. 2019). Howard and colleagues introduced MobileNets with depth-separable convolutions (Howard et al. 2019). However, these compression techniques often impose their own cost.

2.3. Dataset Complexity

Analyzing dataset complexity has always been a challenge for researchers working in machine learning. (Ho and Basu. 2002), working in this field, proposed feature efficiency and class overlap measures for tabular data. (Torralba and Efron. 2011), investigating cross-dataset generalization, found that models overfit to dataset-specific artifacts. (Ethayarajh et al. 2022),

introducing v-available information, measured how much information about labels was present in the learned representations. (Swayamdipta et al. 2009), on the other hand, mapped training dynamics to identify hard and easy examples. However, all of these approaches require pre-training the models.

2.4. Automated Machine Learning

AutoML frameworks aim to automate hyperparameter tuning and model selection. Auto-sklearn uses Bayesian optimization on scikit-learn estimators (Feurer et al. 2015). TPOT uses genetic programming to evolve pipelines (Olson et al. 2016). Recent AutoML systems incorporate multi-objective optimization. Pareto Active Learning balances latency and accuracy (Zuluaga et al. 2016). However, existing AutoML frameworks rarely consider carbon emissions as an optimization objective.

2.5. Carbon-Aware Computing

CodeCarbon 2 performs real-time operations: the first tracks energy production in real time, and the second converts it into CO₂ estimates based on regional energy mixes (Schmidt et al. 2021). Dodge and colleagues have shown that scheduling training during low-carbon hours can reduce emissions by 30-40% (Dodge et al. 2022). However, the use of these tools does not guide model selection, only measures emissions.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Datasets

Nine different image recognition datasets, varying in complexity, scale, and area, were used in the study.

- ✚ **CIFAR-10/100** (Krizhevsky and Hinton. 2009): This dataset contains 50K color images (32×32) across 10 or 100 classes. These two datasets have standard benchmarks that balance simplicity with real-world complexity.
- ✚ **MNIST** (LeCun et al. 2002): Contains handwritten digits. It consists of a total of 10 classes and contains 0K training and 10K test images. It can be used as a baseline reference dataset for minimum complexity.
- ✚ **Fashion-MNIST** (Xiao et al. 2017): Contains fashion products. It consists of a total of 10 classes and contains 60K images. It is an alternative dataset with increased difficulty compared to the MNIST dataset.
- ✚ **Food-101** (Bossard et al. 2014): This dataset, which requires fine-grained recognition requiring texture separation, has a total of 101 food categories and 20K data. STL-10

(Coates et al. 2011): This dataset consists of 10 classes and 5K high-resolution images (96×96) that can be tested for few-shot learning with limited examples.

- ✚ **SVHN** (Netzer et al. 2011): This dataset consists of house numbers from street scenes. The dataset contains 73K images, allowing for real-world number recognition testing with background variability.
- ✚ **Oxford-IIIT Pet** (Parkhi et al. 2012): This dataset, which can be used to test fine-grained breed discrimination, contains a total of 3.7K images from 37 cat and dog breeds.
- ✚ **Flowers-102** (Nilsback and Zisserman. 2008): This dataset, which can be used to test challenging few-shot scenarios with high intra-class variance, consists of a total of 1K images from 102 flower species.

All images in the datasets were resized to 224×224 and normalized to ImageNet statistics. Data augmentation was not applied.

3.2. Model Architectures

Seven different architectures, ranging from traditional machine learning to modern transformer-based architectures, were identified for the decision support system developed in the study.

3.2.1. Machine Learning Models:

Two different approaches were used for the machine learning models used in the study. The first stage involved training the ResNet-18 model to extract meaningful features from raw image data. This approach generated 512-dimensional feature vectors from the global average pooling layer before the final fully connected layer of ResNet-18. This process is called feature extraction and is used to transform raw pixel values into high-level semantic representations. In the next stage, the feature vectors obtained in the first stage were trained with machine learning algorithms.

1. **Random Forest:** In this ensemble learning approach, a forest structure consisting of 100 decision trees was used in the study. Each tree was limited to a maximum depth of 20 to reduce the risk of overfitting. The Gini impurity was used as the splitting criterion, and all CPU cores were activated for parallel computation ($n_jobs=-1$). The ensemble method enhances the generalization ability of the overall model through the voting mechanism of individual trees and can capture nonlinear decision boundaries.
2. **Logistic Regression:** Multinomial logistic regression was used for multi-class classification. L2 regularization ($C=1.0$) was applied to prevent overfitting. Training was performed with a stochastic gradient descent variant optimized for large-scale

problems. This model constitutes the simplest baseline for classification with linear decision boundaries.

3. **XGBoost:** Gradient boosted decision trees algorithm was used in the study as another machine learning algorithm (Chen 2016). Sequential learning was performed with 100 estimators in the model, where each new tree focuses on correcting the errors of previous trees. The maximum depth was set to 10, and all processor cores were activated for parallel computation. XGBoost is considered one of the highest-performance algorithms in feature-based learning.

3.2.2. Deep Learning Models:

1. **MobileNetV3-Small (2.5M parameters):** MobileNetV3, an efficiency-optimized CNN architecture, is specifically designed for mobile and edge devices (Howard et al.2019). It utilizes squeeze-and-excitation modules, inverted residuals, and hard-swish activation functions. Compared to standard CNNs, it offers competitive performance with 10 times less computational cost thanks to depth-separable convolutions.
2. **ResNet-18 (11.2M parameters):** ResNet-18, an 18-layer residual network, uses skip connections, simplifying the training of deep neural networks (He et al. 2016). It is the smallest member of the ResNet family and offers a balanced solution between performance and efficiency.
3. **EfficientNet-B0 (5.3M parameters):** EfficientNet-B0, a CNN architecture, was discovered using neural architecture search (NAS) and uses a compound scaling strategy (Tan and Le. 2019). It achieves the optimal balance between efficiency and accuracy by scaling the resolution, width, and depth dimensions evenly. The architecture, which uses mobile inverted bottleneck convolutions, minimizes the number of parameters.

3.2.3. Transformer-Based Model:

1. **ViT-Tiny (5.7M parameters):** This is a vision transformer that processes images as 16x16 patch arrays using entirely self-attention mechanisms instead of convolutional layers (Dosovitskiy 2020). It is an adaptation of the transformer architecture, which has demonstrated great success in natural language processing, to the image domain.

3.3. Complexity Scoring

A complexity score was calculated for each dataset using five images from 500 samples. Five different metrics were considered in calculating this complexity score:

- i. **Inter-Class Similarity [Inter]:** This metric measures the cosine similarity between average features across classes, and class separability.
- ii. **Edge Density[E]:** The proportion of canny edge pixels indicates structural complexity.
- iii. **Intra-Class Variance [Intra]:** The intra-class pixel variance indicates class homogeneity.
- iv. **Texture Complexity[T]:** The standard deviation of gradient magnitudes captures local pattern variation.
- v. **Spatial Frequency[S]:** The average FFT magnitude captures global pattern scales.

The raw metrics were combined using a min-max normalized and weighted average across the datasets. Equation 1 shows the formula for calculating the complexity score.

$$\text{Complexity} = \frac{25}{100} * E + \frac{25}{100} * T + \frac{25}{100} * \text{Inter} + \frac{15}{100} * \text{Intra} + \frac{10}{100} * S \quad (1)$$

Figure 1 shows the complexity scores of the dataset features calculated with the formula in Equation 1.

Figure 1. Dataset Complexity Ranking

3.4. Training Protocol

All models were trained using a standard set of training values. Deep learning and transformer models were trained with 8 epochs and the AdamW optimizer (learning rate: 0.001), a batch size of 256, cross-entropy loss, and mixed-precision training. Machine learning models were trained using feature extraction with a maximum of 8,000 examples.

CodeCarbon was used to track carbon emissions, tracking actual carbon consumption and converting it to CO₂ based on regional carbon density (Schmidt et al. 2021).

3.5. Green AI Score

A Green AI Score was defined to identify models suitable for the datasets that are the focus of the study, combining model accuracy values [Acc], complexity-capacity match [Match], and carbon efficiency [CE] and Time Efficiency [TE]. Equation 2 shows the Green AI Score formula used in the study.

$$\text{Green AI Score} = \left(\frac{40}{100} * \text{Acc} + \frac{30}{100} * \text{CE} + \frac{20}{100} * \text{Match} + \frac{10}{100} * \text{TE} \right) * \text{Penalty} \quad (2)$$

3.6. Recommendation System

The system, trained on 63 model-dataset experiments (7 models × 9 datasets), estimates Green Scores from 9-dimensional feature vectors containing dataset complexity, visual metrics, gradient boosting regression, model capacity, number of classes, and number of parameters.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

As part of the study, a detailed comparison study was conducted, and a decision support system was created for 9 different datasets based on 63 experiments. Accuracy values ranging from 30.4% to 99.5%, carbon emissions ranging from 0.012g to 8.3g, and training times ranging from 2.6s to 1.788s were achieved.

Figure 2 shows the scatter plot of the datasets according to CO₂ and Accuracy values.

Figure 2. Efficiency Frontiers per Dataset

Machine learning models achieved an average accuracy of 72.4%, while deep learning and transformer-based models achieved an average accuracy of 85.2%.

However, this advantage in accuracy turned out to be a disadvantage for deep learning and transformer-based models in terms of CO₂ consumption. Deep learning and transformer-based

models, which consumed an average of 3.24g of CO₂, consumed 6.2 times more CO₂ than machine learning models, which consumed 0.52g.

Training times also increased as the model improved. Machine learning models complete training in an average of 122 seconds, while this average increases to 674 seconds for advanced models.

Figure 3 shows the performance of the models in the green AI field, based on the datasets, as a result of the Green AI score calculation. As seen in the results, the XGBoost algorithm was the greenest AI, resulting in significantly less CO₂ emissions overall, especially for small and medium-complexity data.

Figure 3. Green Score Heatmap

Table 1 shows which model had the best green AI score for each dataset. In the future, models that demonstrate very strong accuracy but consume a lot of energy will be replaced by models that demonstrate high accuracy but consume less energy.

Table 1. Best Model Selection per Dataset

Dataset	Best Model	Accuracy	CO ₂ (g)	Green AI Score
STL10	Random Forest	94.17%	0.015	86.6
CIFAR100	Random Forest	46.97%	0.072	64.1
CIFAR10	XGBoost	82.62%	0.028	81.1
Oxford Pets	Random Forest	87.00%	0.014	83.8
SVHN	XGBoost	52.15%	0.038	68.3
Food101	XGBoost	38.89%	0.108	58.9
Flowers102	Random Forest	61.01%	0.009	73.8
MNIST	XGBoost	94.14%	0.023	86.0
Fashion MNIST	XGBoost	85.55%	0.025	82.4

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a comprehensive framework and a powerful decision support system for carbon-efficient model selection based on dataset complexity. Nine datasets with different characteristics and 63 experimental studies have demonstrated that intelligent architecture selection can reduce carbon footprint by up to 99.5% without sacrificing performance. The findings revealed a strong correlation ($r = 0.89$) between optimal model capacity and dataset complexity, demonstrating that it is possible to establish a pre-training decision-making mechanism. It is important to characterize model complexity before selecting a model. For tasks with a complexity below 0.4, the default XGBoost or Random Forest models are preferred. Based on the results, it is not recommended to switch to deep learning and transformer-based models unless accuracy exceeds 95% performance is essential. For tasks with medium complexity (0.4-0.7), EfficientNet or MobileNetV3 should be preferred over ResNet and its derivatives, and transformers should be avoided for small datasets. Future work should extend this framework to natural language processing, speech, and multimodal tasks with domain-specific complexity metrics. In a future where AI pervades and permeates every aspect of society, environmental sustainability will become non-negotiable. "Bigger is better" will eventually give way to "optimal is appropriate." This work is envisioned as a guide for the transition to the Green AI era.

REFERENCES

- Bossard, L., Guillaumin, M., & Van Gool, L. (2014, September). Food-101—mining discriminative components with random forests. In European conference on computer vision (pp. 446-461). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Chen, T. (2016). XGBoost: A Scalable Tree Boosting System. Cornell University.
- Coates, A., Ng, A., & Lee, H. (2011, June). An analysis of single-layer networks in unsupervised feature learning. In Proceedings of the fourteenth international conference on artificial intelligence and statistics (pp. 215-223). JMLR Workshop and Conference Proceedings.
- Dodge, J., Prewitt, T., Tachet des Combes, R., Odmark, E., Schwartz, R., Strubell, E., ... & Buchanan, W. (2022, June). Measuring the carbon intensity of ai in cloud instances. In Proceedings of the 2022 ACM conference on fairness, accountability, and transparency (pp. 1877-1894).

- Dosovitskiy, A. (2020). An image is worth 16x16 words: Transformers for image recognition at scale. arXiv preprint arXiv:2010.11929.
- Ethayarajh, K., Choi, Y., & Swayamdipta, S. (2022, June). Understanding dataset difficulty with \mathcal{V} -usable information. In International Conference on Machine Learning (pp. 5988-6008). PMLR.
- Feurer, M., Klein, A., Eggenberger, K., Springenberg, J., Blum, M., & Hutter, F. (2015). Efficient and robust automated machine learning. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 28.
- Han, S., Mao, H., & Dally, W. J. (2015). Deep compression: Compressing deep neural networks with pruning, trained quantization and Huffman coding. arXiv preprint arXiv:1510.00149.
- He, K., Zhang, X., Ren, S., & Sun, J. (2016). Deep residual learning for image recognition. In Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition (pp. 770-778).
- Hinton, G., Vinyals, O., & Dean, J. (2015). Distilling the knowledge in a neural network. arXiv preprint arXiv:1503.02531.
- Howard, A., Sandler, M., Chu, G., Chen, L. C., Chen, B., Tan, M., ... & Adam, H. (2019). Searching for mobilenetv3. In Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF international conference on computer vision (pp. 1314-1324).
- Ho, T. K., & Basu, M. (2002). Complexity measures of supervised classification problems. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 24(3), 289-300.
- Jacob, B., Kligys, S., Chen, B., Zhu, M., Tang, M., Howard, A., ... & Kalenichenko, D. (2018). Quantization and training of neural networks for efficient integer-arithmetic-only inference. In Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition (pp. 2704-2713).
- Krizhevsky, A., & Hinton, G. (2009). Learning multiple layers of features from tiny images.
- Lacoste, A., Luccioni, A., Schmidt, V., & Dandres, T. (2019). Quantifying the carbon emissions of machine learning. arXiv preprint arXiv:1910.09700.
- LeCun, Y., Bottou, L., Bengio, Y., & Haffner, P. (2002). Gradient-based learning applied to document recognition. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 86(11), 2278-2324.
- Morán-Fernández, L., Bolón-Canedo, V., & Alonso-Betanzos, A. (2017). Centralized vs. distributed feature selection methods based on data complexity measures. *Knowledge-based systems*, 117, 27-45.
- Netzer, Y., Wang, T., Coates, A., Bissacco, A., Wu, B., & Ng, A. Y. (2011, December). Reading digits in natural images with unsupervised feature learning. In NIPS workshop on deep learning and unsupervised feature learning (Vol. 2011, No. 5, p. 7).
- Nilsback, M. E., & Zisserman, A. (2008, December). Automated flower classification over a large number of classes. In 2008 Sixth Indian conference on computer vision, graphics & image processing (pp. 722-729). IEEE.
- Olson, R. S., Bartley, N., Urbanowicz, R. J., & Moore, J. H. (2016, July). Evaluation of a tree-based pipeline optimization tool for automating data science. In Proceedings of the genetic and evolutionary computation conference 2016 (pp. 485-492).
- Parkhi, O. M., Vedaldi, A., Zisserman, A., & Jawahar, C. V. (2012, June). Cats and dogs. In 2012 IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition (pp. 3498-3505). IEEE.
- Patterson, D., Gonzalez, J., Le, Q., Liang, C., Munguia, L. M., Rothchild, D., ... & Dean, J. (2021). Carbon emissions and large neural network training. arXiv preprint arXiv:2104.10350.
- Schmidt, V., Goyal, K., Joshi, A., Feld, B., Conell, L., Laskaris, N., ... & Luccioni, S. (2021). CodeCarbon: estimate and track carbon emissions from machine learning computing. Cited on, 20.
- Schwartz, R., Dodge, J., Smith, N. A., & Etzioni, O. (2020). Green ai. *Communications of the ACM*, 63(12), 54-63.
- Strubell, E., Ganesh, A., & McCallum, A. (2019, July). Energy and policy considerations for deep learning in NLP. In Proceedings of the 57th annual meeting of the association for computational linguistics (pp. 3645-3650).
- Swayamdipta, S., Schwartz, R., Lourie, N., Wang, Y., Hajishirzi, H., Smith, N. A., & Choi, Y. (2020). Dataset cartography: Mapping and diagnosing datasets with training dynamics. arXiv preprint arXiv:2009.10795.
- Tan, M., & Le, Q. (2019, May). Efficientnet: Rethinking model scaling for convolutional neural networks. In International conference on machine learning (pp. 6105-6114). PMLR.

- Torralba, A., & Efros, A. A. (2011, June). Unbiased look at dataset bias. In CVPR 2011 (pp. 1521-1528). IEEE.
- Wu, C. J., Raghavendra, R., Gupta, U., Acun, B., Ardalani, N., Maeng, K., ... & Hazelwood, K. (2022). Sustainable ai: Environmental implications, challenges and opportunities. *Proceedings of machine learning and systems*, 4, 795-813.
- Xiao, H., Rasul, K., & Vollgraf, R. (2017). Fashion-mnist: a novel image dataset for benchmarking machine learning algorithms. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1708.07747*.
- Zuluaga, M., Krause, A., & Püschel, M. (2016). e-pal: An active learning approach to the multi-objective optimization problem. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 17(104), 1-32.

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